

From pedestrians to ships: How to model ship traffic using the Optimal Steps Model

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Abstract—Maritime traffic simulations are an essential part of what-if analysis based risk assessment as well as business continuity management. However, only a few microscopic-level approaches exist. Within this paper we propose a conceptual adaptation of the optimal steps model (OSM) from crowd modeling to the maritime domain. Therefore, we highlight existent similarities between the domains and suggest adaptations for the OSM to comply with maritime navigation regulations.

Index Terms—agent-based modeling; traffic simulation; critical infrastructure protection.

I. INTRODUCTION

The term critical infrastructure refers to an infrastructure that provides a vital service for a functioning society. Herein, the transportation sector is considered as one of the major columns, whose purpose is to transport goods and passengers [1]. Regarding freight transport within the European Union, maritime transport leads the modal split with more than two thirds of freight based on tonne-kilometers [2]. Safe and secure traffic within harbors and waterways plays an important role to ensure continuous transport of these goods. Thus, risk management and resilient planning involves data-driven approaches to learn from the past as well as simulations to evaluate the impact of scenarios on the traffic within what-if analysis.

Nowadays, Vessel Traffic Services (VTS) or Automatic Identification System (AIS) data are the main source for ship movement and their analysis allows to evaluate risks for maritime transportation, whereas the scope of the analysis reaches from generating accident probability maps of waterways or harbor entrances to route analysis between harbors [3]. However, a major caveat of these approaches within the domain of critical infrastructure protection is their requirement for representative data sets, that does not exist for all scenarios. Simulation models close this gap by enabling the prediction of a systems behavior in these scenarios.

Unlike road traffic, simulation tools for maritime transportation are sparse. [4] used multi-agent reinforcement learning to forecast vessel movement within zones of the Singapore Strait. However, due to the partitioning in zones, the approach is not feasible for microscopic simulation, i.e., simulations that are able to depict the behaviour of single vessels. ShipNaviSim is one of the few tools for microscopic vessel simulation that uses

AIS data to learn the behavior of individual ships and project this into predefined scenarios [5]. ShipNaviSim is capable of simulating behavior on the sea, it remains untested, whether it might adapt to behavior within harbors.

In other modes of transport including harbor processes, agent-based models are broadly used to depict the behavior of humans or vehicles. [6] reproduced traffic within a container terminal to optimize port logistics and evaluate the impact of traffic congestions within the port by modeling external trucks and internal trailers to serve cranes for cargo loading. This example shows how transport simulation tools developed for road traffic planning adapt to the maritime domain.

For passenger transport within transportation hubs commonly agent-based simulation is used, whereas the agents represent pedestrians. The interaction between pedestrians is commonly modeled either using a social-force model [7] or the optimal steps model (OSM) [8]. The social-force model assumes agents to have a propulsive force leading to evasion of the pedestrians during movement. On the other hand, the optimal steps model allows movement on a continuous space with adaptive evaluation of the agents movement at each step. This property makes it more suitable to depict vessel behavior as it enables modeling the speed dependency of the maneuverability of the ship and allows an easier adaptation on maritime traffic rules. [9] enabled the bi-directional coupling of the optimal steps model with the electrical systems of an airport to depict the infrastructure and therefore enabled the simulation of infrastructures as a socio-technical system for risk analysis and decision-making support. Within this paper, we propose a concept for the adaptation of the optimal steps model to the maritime domain to allow vessel traffic simulation on a microscopic level.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: In Section II the optimal steps model is explained in detail. Then we propose necessary adaptations of the model to adapt to vessel behavior in Section III. Finally, we conclude the contributions of this work, discuss their limitations and give an outlook on further work in Section IV.

II. THE OPTIMAL STEPS MODEL FOR PEDESTRIANS

The optimal steps model (OSM) was introduced by [10] and then continuously improved to serve a couple of purposes

Fig. 1. Discretization of the circles reflected by points. The three arrows represent six possible positions for the next step. [9]

reaching from evacuation scenarios [11] over infection spreading during pandemics [12] to sabotage scenarios at airports [9].

The optimal-steps model merges the strengths of cellular automata with those of social-force approaches. Building on the framework of [8], it introduces two key ingredients: (1) repulsive potentials generated by other pedestrians and by static obstacles, and (2) a travel-time field that measures how long it takes to reach a destination from every point in the room. These ingredients are combined to form a floor-field from which each agent selects an optimal step. These two phases are referred to as navigation and locomotion.

A. Navigation

The floor-field represents a wavefront traveling through the continuum from one destination to another and in occurrence of obstacles can be calculated using the Eikonal equation as given in Equation 1, where $V(\vec{x})$ represents the velocity field at a position \vec{x} and $N(\vec{x})$ the travel time of the wave front from a target area Z to this position.

$$V(\vec{x}) \cdot |\vec{\nabla} N(\vec{x})| = 1, \quad N(\vec{x}) = 0 \text{ for } \vec{x} \in Z \quad (1)$$

As the wavefront cannot pass through obstacles and gets slowed down near them, the velocity field value $V(\vec{x})$ increases linearly from 0 to 1 within a certain distance d_c from the obstacle. If the distance exceeds d_c , the wave travels at a constant speed of 1. Thus, the potential can be expressed as in Equation 2.

$$V(\vec{x}) = \begin{cases} 0, & \vec{x} \in E \\ \min(1, \delta_E(\vec{x}) \cdot \frac{1}{d_c}), & \vec{x} \notin E \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

B. Locomotion

When a pedestrian decides where to move next, the model does not rely solely on the floor-field value. It also takes into account the repulsive influence of nearby agents by performing a local optimization on one or more circles centered on each pedestrian. This allows to keep a continuous trajectory while still exploring a discrete set of candidate positions (illustrated in Figure 1). The orientation of the circle is updated after every step, so to allow the agents to move freely on the plane.

The resulting floor-field is a superposition of the attractive potential $P_t(\vec{x})$ of a target t at position \vec{x} and the repulsive potential $P_{p,i}(\vec{x})$ and $P_{o,j}(\vec{x})$ of pedestrian i and obstacle j , respectively, as given in Equation 3.

Fig. 2. Navigation field at $d_c = 50m$ within the Hamburg Harbor exmple region and Ferry Stop Finkenwerder as source location. Ferry line 62 path is marked as a blue dashed line. Sources/Sinks for traffic are the Elbe to the North Sea on the left (west) and the Norderelbe and Köhlbrand to the right (east).

$$P_l(\vec{x}) = P_t(\vec{x}) + \sum_{i=1, i \neq l}^n P_{p,i}(\vec{x}) + \sum_{j=1}^m P_{o,j}(\vec{x}) \quad (3)$$

To choose the next move the utility function $P_l(\vec{x})$ is evaluated at every point on the discretized circle as well as at the current position. “Large” steps (full walking distance) and “small” steps (half the distance) are introduced using two concentric circles with different radius, whereas each circle is sampled at 32 equally spaced angles, yielding 32 candidate positions per step. The point with the lowest $P_l(\vec{x})$ (i.e., the highest attractive/lowest repulsive value) is selected as the next destination.

III. ADAPTATION ON VESSEL BEHAVIOR

Within this Section we propose an approach how to adapt the optimal steps model to the maritime domain to simulate vessel traffic. Therefore, we address the use of navigation fields and targets at the example of an area on the Elbe and Hamburg Harbor. Furthermore, we elaborate on how to translate properties of ship movement and navigation rules on locomotion.

A. Ship Navigation

The use of floor-field-based navigation for path-planning in maritime environments is already established. [13] proposed solving the Eikonal equation for the navigation of unmanned surface vehicle formations using the fast-marching method and enhanced this using a safety map $M_S(\vec{x})$ based on the uncertainty conditions introduced by [14], which basically translates to a penalty speed in previously defined areas. [15] enhanced this to align with waterway center lines or preferred way points. The potential used for pedestrian navigation as given in Equation 2 already includes a speed penalty and forces ships to keep distance to obstacles. Thus, the use seems appropriate, if d_c is chosen large enough.

Fig. 3. Discretization of the circles at normal (a), low (b) and high velocities. The distance of the evaluated points from the ship's center increases proportional to the speed, while the angle between discretized points behaves anti-proportional. Blue dots mark preferred next positions.

At the example of a harbor area and parts of the Elbe in Hamburg in Figure 2, we show the setup for a possible simulation use case. Cargo ships enter the area from the west and either go into the harbor basin or continue eastwards to the Norderelbe or Kölbrand. Quay areas for unloading in the harbor area are marked as targets. Furthermore, the regional ferry line 62 enters from the east and leaves to the east after stopping at three locations building a list of targets for incoming ferries. The route is depicted as a blue dashed line. Colors depict the outgoing floor-field from the source Ferry Stop Finkenwerder, which guides the ferry movement without any other ships influencing its movement.

In the context of pedestrian movement, pedestrian interaction is modeled using circular repulsive potentials within the pedestrian's domain. However, the transfer of the circular repulsive potential of pedestrians onto ships is inappropriate. In the context of collision inference mapping, a manifold of different ship domains have been developed (see [16] for an overview) and can be used to replace the circular repulsive field by a ship domain field. Here, we suggest using the elliptical field as given in [16], which represents the area around the ship that should not be entered by other ships to avoid collisions.

B. Ship Maneuverability

While pedestrians are very agile regarding their ability to turn, the maneuverability of the ship is dependent on its speed. Therefore, a full circle evaluation at a fixed angle discretization is inappropriate for the search of the optimal step. Thus, we propose to use a set of five beams through these circles determining the evaluation spots, whereas the angle between beams is speed dependent. Furthermore, the radius of the evaluation circles change as it can be seen in Figure 3, where the radius of the evaluation circle increases or decreases proportional to the current ship velocity and the angle between evaluated points on the circle anti-proportional to the speed. At low speeds (≤ 1 kt) the ship is able to nearly turn in place (see Fig 3 b) and at high speeds (≥ 10 kt) only

small course changes are possible per step. This prevents fast turns at high speeds and enables good maneuverability at very low speeds within harbor basins. Large steps are preferred to maintain speed, i.e., points on the outer circle are chosen in equal values of the utility function 3.

C. Ship Evasion, Crossing and Overtaking

The International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea [17], shortly referred to as COLREG [17], are an essential set of rules the simulated ships should follow. Therefore, we modify the rules of choice for the optimal step in a way that allows to model ship behavior during encounters. Herein, we concentrate on the correct evasion of oncoming ships, crossing situations and overtaking. In case of the evasion of an oncoming ship (head-on situation), the goal is to follow COLREG Rule 14, i.e., alter the course to starboard. In a crossing situation, the ship having the other ship (stand-on vessel) on its starboard side is considered the give-away vessel, i.e., it has to evade without crossing the other ships course (COLREG Rules 15-16). In reality, this is often done by altering the course to starboard to steer away from the other ship. In case of overtaking the overtaking ship should stay out of the way in safe distance (COLREG Rule 13).

Figure 4 shows the discretization of the circles during ship evasion (a), crossing situations (b) or overtaking (c). We propose that steps on the outer circle are evaluated first to maintain speed. The step on the outer circle in course direction is preferred, followed by clockwise evaluation on the outer circle. Therefore, it is guaranteed that for head-on situations evasion is conducted to starboard side as depicted in Figure 4 (a). To prevent ships crossing through the ship domain of the oncoming ship using the long step, steps on the outer ring are only chosen, if the point on the inner ring of the same beam is not within the other ship's domain.

The optimal steps model reacts on the crossing situations at the moment, when the first evaluated step is inside the elliptically shaped ship domain resulting in large values of the utility function. Continuing the evaluation along the outer

Fig. 4. Discretization of the circles in occurrence of ship evasion (a), crossing situations (b) or overtaking (c). Blue dots mark preferred next positions for the respective situation.

circle in clockwise direction yields in a preference of the starboard side to evade the other ship. In combination with the previously described angle change and the increase of the evaluation circle radius for fast ships (see Subsection III-B) either a slow down is forced, if all points on the outer circle are within the other ship's domain, or course alterations are done at low speeds (and large evaluation angles) as it is shown in Figure 4 (b).

The elliptical shape of the ship domain reaching behind the other ship automatically leads to the effect of other vessels overtaking on the side they already are, if outer circle points are preferred and steps through the ship domain are prevented as described in the evasion choice process.

IV. SUMMARY & OUTLOOK

Within this paper we have proposed an adaptation of the optimal steps model to the maritime domain for microscopic ship traffic simulation. The floor-field-based navigation is a widespread approach for route planning and navigation. However, the version used within this work does not consider streaming velocities and waves, which have a non-negligible effect on the velocity that should be incorporated in future work, especially for waterway traffic. Moreover, bathymetry data can be included in more detail within the calculation of the navigation fields. The suggested locomotion rules show great potential to cover basic navigation rules, such as COLREG. However, the behavior of vessels in reality is more complicated and demands to cover a lot of edge cases. For crowd management applications, field data, i.e., tracked pedestrian trajectories, were used to cover these cases, validate and further adapt the optimal steps model. Thus, we highly suggest to use AIS trajectory data to validate the approach and further adapt it to suit ship behavior.

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